

SECTION OF HISTORICAL SCIENCES

RELIGIOUS POLICY OF THE RUSSIAN EMPIRE IN KAZAKHSTAN.

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Abstract

This article offers a comprehensive historical overview of the efforts of the Russian Empire to carry out political and administrative reforms, including Russification and Christianization, among the Kazakh population in the late 19th and early 20th centuries. These efforts included various strategies such as opening Russian-language schools, missionary work, and increasing the presence of Russians in Kazakh villages. However, despite these efforts, it seems that most Kazakhs have remained faithful to their traditional cultural and religious values, especially Islam. The text also mentions the emergence of national movements and intellectual resistance to this policy.

Keywords: Kazakhstan, Russian Empire, missionaries, russification, system of upbringing and education.

The political and administrative reforms carried out by the Russian Empire in the second half of the XIX century introduced the population of the Kazakh Steppe into a new administrative structure. At first, the reforms implemented in 1867-1868 were aimed at the colonial administration to intensively develop the Kazakh steppes at its disposal, to make the Kazakhs completely administratively and structurally dependent on the Russian empire, while the administrative and structural measures carried out in the 1890s divided the territory of Kazakhstan into the Orenburg, West Siberian, Turkestan governorates-general, Astrakhan province, and Caucasian military districts. After the introduction of the Kazakh Steppe under the rule of the Russian Empire, the process of reducing the colonized population to not only material but also cultural and spiritual dependence was carried out by the administration of the territory. Along with mass Russification, the opening of the first Russian-language schools also coincided with this time. But the work carried out did not bring results. Because the only thing that became the basis for the preservation of cultural and spiritual existence in the memory of the people was the beliefs of the people and Muslimism. In the XIX century, Tatar mullahs played a special role in raising the literacy of the local population. In Kazakhstan, without a special state education system, Tatars have become the main disseminators of literacy among the Kazakh population. By 1888, 9 private Tatar madrasas, permanently operating in Semipalatinsk, provided education.

Thus, Kazakh children received primary education in Tatar schools in the village. Tatar clergymen – mullahs worked as teachers in these schools. The spread of education among Kazakhs through Tatar mullahs could not but disturb the officials of the Tsarist government. They begin to take a Sekem from the threat of tatarization of the Kazakhs. There was also a suspicion that there could be extremely negative political consequences for Russia. Among the Kazakh intelligentsia, which advocated secular education, there were also dissatisfied with religious and Muslim education. However, it is known that wealthy Kazakhs who support Muslim education provide financial assistance to mad-

rasas and schools. Some Kazakh merchants and businessmen, dissatisfied with the spread of the Russian language among the Kazakhs, and the penetration of Christianity, supported the spread of Muslim education through the Tatar mullahs. Many Kazakh children learned literacy from the village of Mullah.

At first, the Russian Empire did not put forward a measure of Russification of its colonies. But during the above-mentioned administrative measures, he realized the need for it. In addition, the Tsarist government began to receive criticism for the growing influence of the Tatars on the Kazakhs in the confessional, educational, and trade spheres. Now there is a suspicion that the Tatar mullahs may have a negative influence on the Kazakhs.

In this regard, the Russian administration began to tighten anti-Islamic measures. Various missionary movements and religious schools were opened to baptize the local population. Before creating the mission, certain work was carried out to determine the possibility of its occurrence. The missionaries initially sought answers to the following questions:

1. To what extent did Islam develop among Kazakhs?
2. Where and in what ways do they get into them?
3. What will be the measures to weaken it?
4. Under what circumstances can you create a mission without causing any excitement between them?

After studying, the authorities believed that the influence of Tatar mullahs on the Kazakhs and the unification of the Islamic world created favourable conditions for sending missions to the Kazakh land. At the same time, in their opinion, it was believed that the Kazakhs were ready to voluntarily fulfil the desires of Russian culture and part of Russia since it had been quite a long time since they became the Russian boda.

Missionaries such as N. I. Ilminsky, A. I. Alektorov, V. V. Katarinsky, N. P. Ostroumov, specially sent to the Kazakh land, developed special training programs for "Native" children studying in the same schools. The program was aimed at forgetting not only the native language but also customs, traditions, and religion. In 1881, on the initiative of the Holy Synod on the Kazakh land, an institution called the

Kyrgyz spiritual mission was created, the centre of which was Semipalatinsk. Since 1883, fourteen missionary organizations have been opened under the same institution, and seventeen missionary schools have been opened under the same organizations [1]. Several works of Professor scientist, and well-known missionary N. P. Ostroumov, who worked directly with this institution in this field, are published in Kazan and Tashkent, where they describe the analysis and views, methods, and techniques of the adoption of Christianity and culture by the peoples of Central Asia.

In addition to N. P. Ostroumov, another famous missionary N. I. Ilminsky was the most successful representative of missionary movements in Kazakhstan. He wrote that the most effective way to Russify and christen the "buratans" is education. And in the same direction, not only did he perform his mission well, but he left behind a few works that were based on research. Great importance was attached to the Christianization of Tatars, Kazakhs and other non-Russian Muslim peoples of Russia. To spread orthodoxy, religious pamphlets began to be distributed in the country, which served as spiritual food. For this mission, special funds were allocated, which, despite the high cost, began to be provided at a very low price or even free of charge. The Russian Empire continuously carried out not only missionary measures to attract the local population to Christianity, but also the process of Russification of their composition. Russian peasants settled near Kazakh villages. In order to reduce the number of Muslims in this regard, starting with the mass resettlement of Kazakhs, at the Synod Council held on the fifth of April 1912, the Kazakhs were forbidden to sit separately when they were given settled land, they must live next door to the Russian, the number of Russians in each village should be at least twice as large, and only then, no matter what issue is considered, the number of Russians will prevail, which will allow the Kazakhs to accept Orthodoxy as soon as possible [2]. After that, there was great discontent among the Kazakh intelligentsia, who were very tolerant of the policy of the Russian Empire, which was carried out until now. According to the above-mentioned resolution, Alikhan Bukeikhanov wrote a letter to the State Duma and published it in the issue of the newspaper "Rech" dated January 22, 1914. The letter says that Alikhan Bukeikhanov criticized the resolution of the Synod and expressed confidence that the State Duma will make the right decision on this issue.

The Russian Empire published opinions among the people that paradoxically reflect Islam and its values. Especially the mullah-ISHS, the religious leaders among the people, tried to show in the account of those who lead them astray from the Straight Path. Russian-language publications published articles in which various opinions were grouped, denigrating Islam as a religion. For example, in the Journal "Musulmanskyy Mir", published at the beginning of the twentieth century under the Russian Academy of Sciences, we find articles analysing the Koran, comparing it with the Bible, criticizing surahs in conclusion and concluding that the Koran itself is "full of fanaticism". The work of the journal

was mainly aimed at analysing Islamic literature published abroad and providing small information about it. From here one can observe the twofold policy of the colonial government on the Muslim peoples under its jurisdiction.

We said that the expansion of the Kazakh steppe by the Russian Empire was not only economic, but also spiritual. To convert Kazakhs to Christianity, missionaries and local authorities provided the "baptized" with various benefits and benefits, such as tax exemption. Among the Kazakhs, those who converted to Christianity were poor peasants living in border areas, zhataks orphans, and widows. But the Russian missionary Filoret Sinkovsky wrote in his writings that "the vast majority of those who converted to Orthodoxy are poor people, the main reason for their conversion was not because they firmly believed that their religion was worthless, but because of material necessity. Even after the adoption of Christianity, they were indifferent to religion and were not at all willing to delve into it." Such people were then rejected by their village, accusing them of "apostates". There is also evidence of those who sometimes accepted orthodoxy as a whole village and assimilated into Russian villages. Although over time they began to Russify their names and wear them as Russians before their clothes, they did not abandon their traditions and traditions, but partly kept them in their religion. We know about this from a letter to the Kazakh "Kazakh", who was baptized in Sharigi in the Biisk county of Tomsk province. The "Baptists" were attached by local authorities to missionaries to recognize religion. However, there were not a few of them who later returned to Islam.

As a result, as it should be, the result of the missionary movement carried out for almost a century was very poor [3]. Only 226 Kazakhs converted to Orthodoxy from missionary activities carried out in the Turkestan region in 1912-1916. The missionaries themselves also wrote about this: "It is better than nothing" [4]. In addition to bringing Christianity to the Kazakhs, the Tsarist government used various methods to remove Islam from the people. For example, for the construction of mosques-madrasas, the permission of the governor-general was required directly. For the education of the child, it was also obliged to obtain permission from a representative of the authorities. In Turkey, Egypt, Bukhara, and other Eastern countries, those who received a Muslim education were not allowed to work as teachers at the school-Madrasah at all. If the same rule was violated, the fine was paid not only by the teacher but also by the parents of the child taught by that teacher. In the same way, it has increased measures such as bans and obtaining permits in any matters related to Islam. In comparison, in the Kazakh regions, government offices allocated land and funds for the construction of churches, monasteries, and parishes to strengthen the position of Christianity. However, the Tsarist authorities categorically did not oppose the construction of a mosque-Madrasah between the country. He was afraid that such radical measures would anger the people and even lead to uprisings. For example, the governor-general of the Turkestan region, General of the infantries S. M. Dukhovskiy, in his full report to the

emperor in 1899, said that there are about 15 million Muslims in the Empire in total, although they look subordinate, among them there are often those who agitate for an uprising. The report once again states that Muslims are not friends with Christians based on Sharia and says that it is a mistake to think that the region is peaceful. After that, the Tsarist government had a reason to tremble. After all, they were very worried about the Andijan uprising in 1898.

The Tsarist authorities were very upset by the fact that the Turkic-speaking peoples inhabiting one and the same territory united against themselves. In order to prevent such situations, the program of classes in missionary schools built on the Kazakh land was maximally Russified, and the history of Russia, the language, and orthodox religious lessons were maximized. At the same time, Muslim-Kazakh children studying at the boarding school, as far as possible, did not return to their villages during the holidays. The reason was that after returning to his parents, the child forgot what he had read, and learned, and as mentioned above, was afraid that Muslims would gather and gain spiritual strength.

At the beginning of the last century, in Russia, where about 20 million Muslims live, the creation of a religious administration was one of the most pressing issues. In particular, the lack of a special office to consider the issues of the Islamic religion was the first item on the state's agenda. At this time, the Christian faith had its own missionary organizations, which received good financial support from the state. In comparison, there was no system nor Finance in the institutions dedicated to the Islamic religion. In addition, there were many restrictions on their activities, both on the part of the state and on the part of the law.

This is how the Muslim clergy were divided in Russia during the period mentioned in the Empire:

- 1) Tauride Muslim administration in the Western provinces and Crimea.
- 2) Majilis headed by Sheikh-ul-Islam, which has a special right on the territory of the South Caucasus.
- 3) the Department subordinate to the governor-general in the Caspian and Turkestan territories.
- 4) administrative and civil organizations of Semipalatinsk, Akmola, Uralsk and Turgai regions.
- 5) the North Caucasus region, subordinate to the Orenburg Mufti and its administration.

About the activities of missionaries seeking mass baptism of Kazakhs in the Kazakh steppe, the scientist, researcher K. Kemengeruly wrote that the Russians began a policy of baptism of Kazakhs, for the implementation of which missionaries came out of the public. However, the vast majority of Kazakhs who feel this rawness, as a means against it, on the contrary, say that they are more adapted to recognize and adhere to Islam. Most of the baptized wrote that they lived in the city of Kazakh workers who were interested in money, those who were in a state of death during hunger, and those who could not find refuge in their tribe. [5]

The Russian Empire, when building its schools on the Kazakh land, comprehensively thought out the directions of assimilation and Russification of the local population, created the maximum conditions for non-

unification with other Muslim peoples, non-interaction of schools. A. Salikhov, who was at the head of the Islamic movements on the Kazakh land, said: as a result of the policy "divide ahead, dance", mixed schools of Russian-Kazakh, Russian-Bashkir, etc. were opened. This division will weaken their resistance and accelerate the process of Russification."

No matter what measures were taken in relation to the spiritual life of the Kazakhs, they remained true to their long-standing traditions. The *novoe Vremya* newspaper wrote in 1911: "we amazed the imagination of the local population with miracles of technical culture, Railways, telegraphs, all kinds of uses of electricity, etc. But our spiritual culture has not yet touched the soul of a Turkistan Muslim. Such an assessment, in our opinion, is characteristic of all Muslims who lived in Tsarist Russia.

At the beginning of the twentieth century, control over the Muslim religion by the government increased, the gendarmerie kept under strict control any measures related to religion. During this period, the religious consciousness of the Muslim peoples of Russia also reawakened, ideas of unification and consolidation began to appear in one centre. At the beginning of the twentieth century, a force of great political importance was formed among the followers of the Islamic religion of the Empire. With the help of Muslim figures in the territory, where the above-mentioned religious authorities were located, the movement followed the idea of the unification of the Turks into one centre with the support of the Ottoman Empire. Events that failed in Russia, such as the revolution of a bourgeois-democratic nature, the convocation of Deputies to the Duma and others, became a kind of alarm and had a special impact on the political consciousness of the peoples who professed Islam. Political organizations appeared in many large Muslim centres, and in the Duma, Muslim deputies United into one faction. Pan Islamism, among the Muslim intellectuals of Turkish origin, the ideas of Pan-Turkism emerged. All of them began their actions with the aim of freeing the Muslim peoples from the shackles of colonial oppression. Despite strict censorship and pressure from the leadership, they began to publish their first Islamic-themed periodicals. Before the first Russian Revolution, there were only two periodicals published by Muslims in all of Russia: the first was the Tatar "translator", the second was the "Steppe Wilayat newspaper". After the granting of freedom of speech by the royal decree of 1905, more than 30 Muslim newspapers and magazines appeared in the Empire.

The beginning of the Tsarist government's involvement in religion and land, language and education caused discontent among the Kazakh society and intellectuals. As a result, in June 1905, at the Koyandy fair, a petition was sent to the chairman of the Council of Ministers of Russia P. A. Stolypin, signed by about 15 thousand Kazakhs with the demands of the people. In addition to the most important issues in Kazakh society, the petition addressed acute and urgent issues such as the arrival of missionaries, the implementation of the policy of Russification, education issues, the unjustified persecution of Islam and Muslims, the seizure of the vast territories of the Kazakh land and the transfer

of these lands to foreign settlers, the reduction of pasture lands and the trampling of the rights of the common people. The petition, written with great literacy and signed by Kazakh intellectuals who openly and clearly expressed their wishes, is a very important historical document that occupies a special place in the history of Kazakhstan.

The establishment of the Soviet government introduced the people to a power that was in no way similar to the previous one and had a completely different approach to religion. For the new authorities, All Russia, including Kazakhstan, was a symbol of ignorance and savagery. In a short time, churches and mosques, madrasas and temples, prayer houses and sacred places were closed or destroyed. Some of the buildings were commissioned for special authorities, as entertainment venues and stables. During the Civil War, the sound of adhan and church bells were banned, and imams and clergy in general were forbidden to walk outside in sardars and religious clothing. And people who disobeyed this rule and the law were punished as a cause of panic, and sometimes even driven away. The authorities, not considering the people and their beliefs, trampled on the norms of human law, ignored the needs of the people, increased the discontent of the people. The government, which forced the Kazakh people to the Christian faith and completely exhausted them by the fact that there was no religion, by its actions did not consider one of the protests and continued to pursue its goals.

In conclusion, there is reason to believe that the attempts of the Russian Empire for a century to transfer

all Muslim peoples to Russification and orthodoxy did not bring any results. This, on the contrary, created the conditions for the emergence of national movements of the size of the Empire and the formation of the intelligentsia. He formed a group of intellectuals who wanted national liberation within the Kazakhs. In addition, the work of the missionaries did not alienate the Kazakhs from Islam, but, on the contrary, brought the people closer to Islam.

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